

Data Quality Audit of the UKRI Gateway to Research Export

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Abstract

This audit note summarises the initial data-quality assessment performed on a raw UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Gateway to Research (GtR) export before constructing an enhanced analysis-ready database. The aim of the audit was to understand whether the raw files could support comparative metascience analysis of funding instruments without further cleaning or enrichment. We examined duplicates and near-duplicates, missing foreign-key references, organisation–person alignment across relationship tables, and initial project classification coverage. The audit showed that the raw GtR records are valuable but not directly analysis-ready: relationship tables contain duplicate or near-duplicate rows, several project relationship tables reference organisations absent from the master organisation file, organisation identities are fragmented, and project-, organisation-, and person-level relationship tables are not fully aligned. Furthermore, we identified malformed rows where quoting errors produce an unexpected number of parsed columns. These findings motivate the cleaning, enrichment, and derived analytical variables of the GTR data.

1 Purpose and Scope

Gateway to Research (GtR) ¹ is UKRI’s public record of funded research and innovation projects. It provides project-level information about awards, organisations, people, project partners, classifications, and reported outputs. In this audit, we focus on the exported relational CSV files underlying these records, rather than on the public web interface, because the aim is to assess whether the raw data can support comparative metascience analysis.

The files include funded projects, organisations, people, project–organisation links, project–person links, project partners, project classifications, and outcome records. The audit did not aim to correct all errors directly (this was done later by a set of heuristic developed by the project). Instead, it identified the main data-quality and modelling issues that had to be addressed before the data could support comparative analysis across funding instruments.

2 Audit Inputs

The audit used CSV files from the raw GtR export, stored locally under the project data directory. The principal files inspected were:

- `project5_funded_project.csv`: core project records;
- `project5_ukri_organisation.csv`: master organisation records;
- `project5_ukri_person.csv`: master person records;

¹<https://www.ukri.org/publications/gateway-to-research-guide/a-guide-to-gateway-to-research/>

- `project5_funded_projectorganisation.csv`: project–organisation relationships;
- `project5_funded_projectperson.csv`: project–person–organisation relationships and investigator roles;
- `project5_funded_projectpartner.csv`: project partner relationships;
- `project5_funded_projectclassification.csv`: project classification, topic, and subject information;
- outcome files covering publications, policy outputs, dissemination, collaborations, spinouts, further funding, intellectual property, technical products, creative products, research materials, databases/models, and other outputs.

The core project file contained 85,627 funded project records. These records were later loaded into a project-centred database, but the audit was performed first to understand the structure, quality, and consistency of the raw files. Figure 1 shows the relationship between the main files used in the audit and their simplified database representation. Note that the raw GtR export contains additional outcomes files (see Annex B), so the full database includes further outcome tables not shown in this simplified figure.

Figure 1: Main GtR audit inputs and their mapping into the original project-centred database.

3 Audit Method

The audit combined six types of checks:

1. **Duplicate and near-duplicate detection:** identify repeated records or repeated composite keys in relationship tables.
2. **Foreign-key checks:** verify whether identifiers referenced in relationship tables exist in the corresponding master tables.
3. **Cross-table consistency checks:** compare organisation participation across project–organisation, project–partner, and project–person tables.

4. **Initial project classification checks:** estimate the coverage of a first responsive-mode heuristic using project scheme and call metadata.
5. **CSV parsing checks:** identify malformed rows where quoting errors produce an unexpected number of parsed columns.
6. **Organisation-identity checks:** identify cases where multiple organisation records appear to represent the same real-world organisation through name, address, source-system, and similarity-based evidence.

The audit (see Table 1) was implemented using Python scripts that produced both machine-readable CSV outputs and human-readable notes.

Table 1: Audit scripts and purpose.

Script	Purpose
<code>analyze_dupes.py</code>	Duplicate detector using a user-defined composite key.
<code>dupes_ProjectClassification.py</code>	Checks duplicate and near-duplicate records in project classifications.
<code>dupes_ResponsiveOpportunity.py</code>	Checks duplicate rows in responsive-opportunity records.
<code>check_fk_projectorganisation.py</code>	Checks whether project-organisation records reference existing projects and organisations.
<code>check_fk_projectpartner.py</code>	Checks whether project-partner records reference existing projects and organisations.
<code>check_fk_projectperson.py</code>	Checks whether project-person records reference existing projects, organisations, and people.
<code>analyze_org_person_alignment.py</code>	Compares organisations in project-organisation, project-partner, and project-person tables.
<code>analyze_projects.py</code>	Produces initial project-level summaries and a first responsive-mode classification.
<code>link_projects_to_opportunities.py</code>	Attempts to link projects to opportunity records using exact and substring matching.
<code>check_error_csv.py</code>	Checks CSV files for malformed rows where the number of parsed columns does not match the expected schema.
<code>fix_lines_csv.py</code>	Repairs known malformed CSV lines; configured here for the publication file but adaptable to similar quoting issues in other files.

4 Audit Results

4.1 Duplicate and Near-Duplicate Records

Duplicate and near-duplicate records were found in key relationship tables. Table 2 summarises the main findings.

Table 2: Duplicate and near-duplicate findings.

Table	Rows	Rows in duplicate groups	Groups
<code>funded_projectclassification</code>	238,544	94	47
<code>funded_projectpartner</code>	123,999	70,332	28,705
<code>funded_projectperson</code>	237,868	0	0

For `funded_projectclassification`, duplicate groups were identified using the composite key over project, classification, research-topic, and research-council type identifiers. These rows share the same conceptual classification key but may differ in values such as percentage funding. For `funded_projectpartner`, duplicate groups were identified using a composite key over project, organisation, partner role, and organisation key. These rows often differ in contribution-related fields such as cash contribution, in-kind contribution, or co-funding percentage. For `funded_projectperson`, no duplicate rows were detected under the composite key over project, organisation, person, and investigator role. This does not imply that the table is free of data-quality issues; as shown in Table 3, the same table contains missing organisation references.

These findings matter because duplicate relationship rows can inflate counts of classifications, partner organisations, and partner contributions if the raw tables are aggregated directly.

4.2 Missing Organisation References

Foreign-key checks showed that several relationship tables reference organisation identifiers not present in the master organisation file. Table 3 summarises the results.

Table 3: Missing references identified by foreign-key checks.

Relationship table	Rows	Missing projects	Missing organisation ref.
<code>funded_projectorganisation</code>	395,969	0	51,635
<code>funded_projectpartner</code>	123,999	0	2,164
<code>funded_projectperson</code>	237,868	0	54,518

The check for `funded_projectperson` also found zero missing person identifiers against the master person file. Therefore, in these checks, referential-integrity problems were concentrated on organisation references rather than project or person references.

These missing organisation references matter because organisation-level analyses, such as counting participating organisations, identifying lead organisations, reconstructing collaborations, or assigning sector and subsector labels, depend on being able to resolve organisation identifiers consistently against the master organisation table.

4.3 Duplicate Organisation Identities

The audit also identified duplicate organisation identities in `project5_ukri_organisation.csv`. This is distinct from the missing-reference problem reported above. In this case, the organisation record exists, but the same real-world organisation may appear under multiple raw `EntityID` values, with different name strings, address variants, or source-system representations.

We identified these cases by comparing organisation names and associated metadata across the organisation records. Candidate duplicate identities were detected using fuzzy name matching, token-normalised similarity, address information, country and city fields, website metadata, and source-system information. Particular care was needed for generic organisation names, multi-country organisations, and university-name inversions, where apparent similarity does not always imply that two records refer to the same real-world organisation. For example, Table 4 illustrates how several raw organisation records may represent variants of the same real-world organisation while still appearing under different raw identifiers.

The audit indicates that approximately 63,598 raw organisation records correspond to approximately 58,000 distinct organisation identities, suggesting that several thousand raw organisation records are repeated or variant representations of the same real-world organisations. This shows that organisation identity fragmentation is widespread enough to affect organisation-level analysis. Without identity resolution, counts of participating organisations, lead organisations,

Table 4: Example of duplicate organisation identity variants.

Raw organisation ID	Raw organisation name
OrgID_1	University of Edinburgh
OrgID_2	The University of Edinburgh
OrgID_3	Edinburgh University
OrgID_4	Univ. of Edinburgh

project partners, and collaboration networks may be fragmented across multiple raw organisation identifiers.

4.4 Organisation–Person Alignment

The audit checked whether organisation information was consistent across the three main tables: `funded_projectorganisation`, `funded_projectpartner`, and `funded_projectperson`. The purpose was to understand whether a single relationship table could be safely used to reconstruct project collaboration networks. Three mismatch classes were examined:

1. **Project-organisation only:** organisations listed as involved in a project but with no corresponding people linked to the same organisation on that project.
2. **Project-partner only:** partner organisations listed for a project but with no corresponding individuals linked to that partner organisation on the same project.
3. **Project-person only:** a person’s organisation appears in the project-person table but does not appear in the project-organisation or project-partner table for that project.

The project-level alignment summary reported 85,627 projects scanned and 85,266 projects with at least one mismatch. This means that almost all projects showed at least one alignment mismatch across the project–organisation, project-partner, and project-person views of participation. This does not necessarily mean that each project record is unusable; rather, it shows that the tables encode different aspects of participation and should not be treated as interchangeable.

Table 5 reports the corresponding row-level mismatch counts. These counts describe the number of relationship rows affected by each mismatch type, not the number of distinct projects.

Table 5: Detailed organisation–person alignment mismatch counts.

Mismatch class	Rows
Project-organisation only: organisation has no corresponding linked people	314,973
Project-partner only: partner organisation has no corresponding linked people	80,856
Project-person only: person’s organisation absent from organisation/partner tables	78,228

The row-level mismatch outputs further show that the largest discrepancy is in project–organisation records without corresponding people, followed by partner organisations without linked people and person-affiliation organisations absent from the project–organisation and partner tables. For analysis, this implies that collaboration reconstruction must be explicit about which relationship table is being used. It also motivates derived tables and dashboard views that separate lead organisations, partners, people, roles, and affiliations rather than collapsing them into a single unqualified participation relation.

4.5 Initial Responsive-Mode Coverage Check

An initial project-level analysis was performed to estimate the coverage of responsive-mode projects using scheme and call metadata. This was an exploratory precursor to the later, broader project-type classification used in the enhanced database. The initial project file contained 85,627 projects. The first responsive-mode heuristic classified 32,594 projects as responsive and 53,033 as non-responsive or unclear. The breakdown by reason was:

Table 6: Initial responsive-mode classification summary.

Reason	Projects
No match	43,774
Matched scheme or call heuristic	32,594
Directed programme pattern	7,450
Ignored by keyword	1,809

This check showed that scheme and call fields contain useful signals for funding-instrument classification, but also that a binary responsive/non-responsive label was insufficient for the broader analysis. This motivated the later project-type taxonomy covering applicant-led, thematic, training, fellowship, infrastructure, institutional, follow-up, and uncertain categories.

4.6 Publication CSV Parsing Errors

The audit also identified parsing errors in `project5_funded_publication.csv`, which is one of the output files. Around 50 lines in the file contained malformed quoted strings, mainly open quotation marks without corresponding closing quotation marks. These errors created artificial attributes or columns when the file was parsed as CSV.

This issue matters because the expected schema for the publication file contains 35 columns. Rows affected by malformed quoting produced a different number of parsed columns, which prevented reliable loading into the database without preprocessing.

Two supporting scripts were used to diagnose and repair this issue. The script `check_error_csv.py` checks CSV files for rows where the number of parsed columns does not match the expected schema and reports the affected files and line numbers. The script `fix_lines_csv.py` was configured to repair the malformed lines in `project5_funded_publication.csv`. Although the repair script was configured for this particular file, the same approach could be adapted for other CSV files if similar malformed quoting issues are found in future exports.

5 Interpretation

The audit showed that the raw GtR export is a valuable source of administrative funding information but cannot be treated as analysis-ready. The main issues are not isolated errors; they reflect the fact that the data were designed for administrative recording and discovery rather than for comparative longitudinal analysis. The most important implications are:

- **Counts over relationship tables require deduplication:** direct aggregation over partner or classification tables can over-count participation, classifications, and contribution-related values.
- **Organisation identifiers require identity resolution:** missing organisation references and duplicate organisation identities make organisation-level analysis unreliable if raw organisation identifiers are treated as stable real-world organisation identities.

- **Participation has multiple meanings:** project organisations, partners, and person affiliations encode different views of involvement and should be modelled separately.
- **The unit of analysis must be explicit:** project-level, organisation-level, partner-level, person-level, and classification-level analyses require different counting rules and should not be derived from a single unqualified participation relation.
- **Derived analytical labels are required:** project type, applicant-led status, career-stage flags, sector/subsector labels, and grant-family identifiers are not consistently available in the raw records.
- **Raw CSV files may require syntactic repair before loading:** malformed quoting in publication records can create artificial columns and prevent rows from matching the expected schema, so import pipelines need validation and repair steps before relational loading.

These audit findings directly motivate the enhanced database and enrichment pipeline developed within the *What is Unique about Responsive Mode projects?* project, including deduplicated relationship views, organisation identity-resolution mechanisms, separated participation models, loading-time validation, and derived analytical variables for comparative metascience analysis.

A Example Commands

The following examples illustrate the audit commands used to generate the CSV outputs and notes. Paths should be adjusted to the local project layout.

A.1 Duplicate detection for project classifications

```
python dupes_ProjectClassification.py \
  --input ../../gtr_database/datafiles/project5_funded_projectclassification.csv \
  --out-prefix projectclassification
```

A.2 Duplicate detection for project partners

```
python analyze_dupes.py \
  --input ../../gtr_database/datafiles/project5_funded_projectpartner.csv \
  --keys ProjectEntityID OrganisationEntityID PartnerRole OrganisationKey \
  --drop-tablepk --null-safe \
  --out-prefix projectpartner
```

A.3 Foreign-key check for project–organisation links

```
python check_fk_projectorganisation.py \
  --projectorganisation ../../gtr_database/datafiles/
  project5_funded_projectorganisation.csv \
  --project ../../gtr_database/datafiles/project5_funded_project.csv \
  --organisation ../../gtr_database/datafiles/project5_ukri_organisation.csv \
  --out-prefix projectorganisation
```

A.4 Foreign-key check for project-person links

```
python check_fk_projectperson.py \  
--projectperson ../../gtr_database/datafiles/project5_funded_projectperson.csv \  
--project ../../gtr_database/datafiles/project5_funded_project.csv \  
--organisation ../../gtr_database/datafiles/project5_ukri_organisation.csv \  
--person ../../gtr_database/datafiles/project5_ukri_person.csv \  
--out-prefix projectperson
```

A.5 Organisation-person alignment check

```
python analyze_org_person_alignment.py \  
--projectorganisation ../../gtr_database/datafiles/  
project5_funded_projectorganisation.csv \  
--projectpartner ../../gtr_database/datafiles/project5_funded_projectpartner.csv \  
--projectperson ../../gtr_database/datafiles/project5_funded_projectperson.csv \  
--out-prefix alignment
```

A.6 Initial project analysis

```
python analyze_projects.py \  
--input ../../gtr_database/datafiles/project5_funded_project.csv \  
--out-prefix projects_analysis
```

A.7 CSV parsing check for publication records

```
python check_error_csv.py \  
--input ../../gtr_database/datafiles/project5_funded_publication.csv \  
--expected-columns 35
```

A.8 Repair malformed publication CSV lines

```
python fix_lines_csv.py \  
--input ../../gtr_database/datafiles/project5_funded_publication.csv \  
--output ../../gtr_database/datafiles/project5_funded_publication_fixed.csv
```

B Raw GtR Export Files

Table 7 summarises the principal raw GtR CSV files considered when constructing the project-centred database. The audit focused primarily on the project, organisation, person, project-organisation, project-person, project-partner, and project-classification files, but the full export also contains outcome files, which are used later in the project.

Table 7: Summary of raw GtR export files.

File	Summary
project5_funded_project.csv	Central file containing funded project records, including identifiers, grant references, project metadata, titles, abstracts, dates, scheme/call information, funding values, organisations, and status fields.
project5_funded_projectorganisation.csv	Organisations formally linked to projects, including relationship type and administrative metadata.
project5_funded_projectpartner.csv	Partner organisations listed for projects, including partner role, cash and in-kind contributions, and co-funding percentage.
project5_funded_projectperson.csv	People linked to projects, each associated with an organisation and investigator role.
project5_funded_projectclassification.csv	Project classifications by research topic, including classification descriptors, keywords, and funding percentages.
project5_ukri_organisation.csv	Master organisation file, including organisation names, types, addresses, countries, identifiers, and status metadata.
project5_ukri_person.csv	Master person file, including person identifiers, names, titles, initials, replacement information, and source-system metadata.
project5_funded_organisationunit.csv	Organisational sub-units, such as departments, linked back to organisations.
project5_funded_projectparticipantvalues.csv	Participant organisations in projects, including financial values such as offer grant and project cost.
project5_funded_projectstudentshipparent.csv	Project-project self-relationship linking projects to parent studentships.
project5_funded_publication.csv	Publication outcomes linked to projects, including DOI, publication venue metadata, titles, dates, and authors.
project5_funded_collaboration.csv	Collaboration outcomes linked to projects, including description, organisation, country, sector, PI contribution, and start year.
project5_funded_dissemination.csv	Engagement and dissemination outcomes, including activity name, form, year, geographic reach, audience, and impact.
project5_funded_policy.csv	Policy-related outcomes, including type of influence, methods, geographic reach, impact, and policy areas influenced.
project5_funded_impactsummary.csv	Narrative project-impact summaries, including beneficiaries, sector, year, contribution methods, and description.
project5_funded_keyfinding.csv	Key findings reported as outcomes, including descriptions, exploitation pathways, and non-academic uses.
project5_funded_furtherfunding.csv	Follow-on funding linked to projects, including funding organisation, reference, value, sector, and dates.
project5_funded_intellectualproperty.csv	Intellectual-property outcomes, such as patents or licences, including type, stage, year granted, licensing status, and description.

File	Summary
<code>project5_funded_spinout.csv</code>	Spin-out company outcomes, including company details, year established, employees, registration, IP exploited, and impact.
<code>project5_funded_creativeproduct.csv</code>	Artistic and creative outputs, such as artworks or performances, including description, type, year produced, and impact.
<code>project5_funded_technicalproduct.csv</code>	Technical product outcomes, including product type, open-source status or licence, year provided, description, and impact.
<code>project5_funded_prodint.csv</code>	Product and intervention outcomes, such as prototypes or clinical trials, including product name, type, development stage, achievements, and impact.
<code>project5_funded_databaseandmodel.csv</code>	Research databases and models, including description, material type, year produced, provision to others, and impact.
<code>project5_funded_researchmaterial.csv</code>	Research materials, including software and datasets, with material type, open-source status, provision to others, and description.
<code>project5_funded_otheroutput.csv</code>	Miscellaneous outputs, including media, broadcasts, reports, beneficiaries, publication details, and cleansed descriptions.
<code>project5_funded_exploitationmechanism.csv</code>	Exploitation-mechanism outcomes, such as companies or spin-offs; largely empty in the current dataset.

C Audit Output Files

The audit generated structured CSV files for inspection and human-readable note files. The most relevant outputs include:

- `projectclassification_duplicates_full.csv` and `projectclassification_dupe_summary.csv`;
- `projectpartner_duplicates_full.csv` and `projectpartner_dupe_summary.csv`;
- `projectorganisation_missing_organisations.csv`;
- `projectpartner_missing_organisations.csv`;
- `projectperson_missing_organisations.csv`;
- `alignment_project_summary_mismatches.csv`;
- `alignment_po_only_missing_persons.csv`;
- `alignment_partner_only_missing_persons.csv`;
- `alignment_person_only_missing_orgs.csv`;
- `projects_analysis_all.csv`.

The supporting audit outputs and scripts, including generated CSV files are available upon request. Requests for access should be sent to either the Project Lead, Chris Daley (C.Daley@lse.ac.uk), or the Project Co-Lead, Rosa Filgueira (r.filgueira@epcc.ed.ac.uk).